

Complexing Behaviour of N-Cyclo Hexyl Benzothiazole Sulphonamide with Cu(II), Mn(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Fe(III)

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Metal complexes of the type ML_2X_2 and $M'L_2X_2$, [M=Cu(II), Mn(II), Ni(II) or Co(II); M'=Fe(III); X=Cl⁻, CH₃COO⁻, NO₂⁻ or C₆H₅(NO₂)₂O⁻ and L=N-cyclo hexyl benzothiazole sulphonamide] have been synthesized and characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility measurements and spectral studies. The ligand behave as a bidentate chelating agent in all the complexes. All the complexes exhibit octahedral stereochemistry. They were screened for fungicidal activity against *Drechslera tetramera*, *Alternaria alternata* and *Fusarium oxysporum*.

THERE has been considerable interest in recent years in the study of complexes with benzothiazole, imidazole and thiazole ligands¹⁻⁴. A perusal of literature shows that no work on transition metal complexes of N-cyclo hexyl benzothiazole sulphonamide has been carried out. We report here the preparation and characterisation of Cu(II), Mn(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Fe(III) complexes with N-cyclo hexyl benzothiazole sulphonamide. The newly synthesized complexes were also screened against different fungi.

Material and methods: All the chemicals used were either C. P. or A. R. grade. The ligand was used after recrystallisation.

Preparation of metal complexes: An alcoholic solution of the appropriate metal salt (1 mole) was refluxed with an alcoholic solution of the ligand (2 mole) for 0.5 hr. The reaction mixture was concentrated to half its volume. Solid complex separated out on cooling which was filtered, washed successively with ethanol and ether and dried *in vacuo*.

The analysis of metal, sulphur and nitrogen were carried out by standard methods. IR spectra of the ligand and complexes were recorded on a Beckmann spectrophotometer model IR-20 in the range 4000-200 cm⁻¹. Magnetic susceptibility measurements of complexes were done by Gouy's method at room temp. using mercury tetrathiocyanato cobaltate as calibrant. The results are given in Table 1.

All the complexes and ligands were screened for their fungicidal activity using three different fungi by growth method.

Results and Discussion

On comparing the infrared spectra of the ligand with those of the complexes, it was found that the positions of most of the bands had shifted. The

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA

Complex	%N	%S	%M	Magnetic susceptibility B. M.
	Found (Calcd.)	Found (Calcd.)	Found (Calcd.)	
L	9.50 (9.45)	21.50 (21.52)	—	—
(CuL ₂)(NO ₂) ₂	10.88 (10.90)	16.58 (16.54)	8.20 (8.15)	1.85
(MnL ₂)(NO ₂) ₂	10.91 (10.89)	16.55 (16.60)	7.08 (7.13)	6.00
(NiL ₂)(NO ₂) ₂	10.86 (10.84)	16.60 (16.54)	7.52 (7.57)	3.16
(CoL ₂)(NO ₂) ₂	10.88 (10.88)	16.55 (16.51)	7.58 (7.61)	4.95
(FeL ₂)(NO ₂) ₂	11.17 (11.24)	16.92 (16.99)	5.00 (4.99)	5.89
(CuL ₂)(OAc) ₂	7.29 (7.23)	16.60 (16.54)	8.15 (8.21)	1.87
(MnL ₂)(OAc) ₂	7.42 (7.39)	16.75 (16.70)	7.12 (7.18)	5.87
(NiL ₂)(OAc) ₂	7.22 (7.28)	16.70 (16.65)	7.61 (7.63)	3.19
(CoL ₂)(OAc) ₂	7.31 (7.28)	16.66 (16.64)	7.65 (7.67)	4.92
(FeL ₂)(OAc) ₂	7.42 (7.40)	17.08 (17.13)	5.02 (4.97)	5.94
(CuL ₂)(Cl) ₂	7.72 (7.70)	17.66 (17.61)	8.80 (8.74)	1.86
(MnL ₂)(Cl) ₂	7.82 (7.79)	17.85 (17.82)	7.62 (7.66)	5.90
(NiL ₂)(Cl) ₂	7.77 (7.75)	17.80 (17.79)	8.11 (8.13)	3.18
(CoL ₂)(Cl) ₂	7.79 (7.75)	17.68 (17.72)	8.19 (8.17)	5.08
(FeL ₂)(Cl) ₂	7.92 (7.99)	18.32 (18.28)	5.36 (5.31)	5.99
(CuL ₂)[C ₆ H ₅ (NO ₂) ₂ O] ₂	12.61 (12.59)	11.48 (11.51)	5.80 (5.71)	1.88
(MnL ₂)[C ₆ H ₅ (NO ₂) ₂ O] ₂	12.55 (12.69)	11.65 (11.60)	4.90 (4.98)	5.88
(NiL ₂)[C ₆ H ₅ (NO ₂) ₂ O] ₂	12.58 (12.65)	11.60 (11.56)	5.25 (5.30)	3.20
(CoL ₂)[C ₆ H ₅ (NO ₂) ₂ O] ₂	12.60 (12.64)	11.54 (11.56)	5.35 (5.32)	4.98
(FeL ₂)[C ₆ H ₅ (NO ₂) ₂ O] ₂	12.98 (12.90)	11.80 (11.78)	8.40 (8.42)	5.90

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bands for sulphonamide group observed at 1305 and 1180 cm^{-1} in the ligand were shifted to 1325-1315 and 1170-1150 cm^{-1} , respectively. $\nu\text{C-S}$ observed at 640 cm^{-1} in the ligand was shifted to a position below 600 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes. In all the complexes a new band appeared around 500 cm^{-1} which is assigned to M-N band. These evidences clearly show that complexation is taking place through the S of thiazole ring and N of sulphonamide group.

The asymmetric and symmetric C=O stretching frequencies of acetate ion expected at 1578 and 1425 cm^{-1} , respectively are observed around 1550-1530 and 1450-1435 cm^{-1} , respectively in acetate complexes. The changes in these modes on complexation suggest that acetate group behaves as a unidentate ligand in all the acetate complexes⁵.

The magnetic moment values of the Cu(II) complexes are in the range of 1.84-1.88 B. M. The μ_{eff} values of the complexes suggest an octahedral or distorted octahedral stereochemistry⁶. All the copper complexes show an electronic spectral band in the region 13000-16000 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the transition ${}^3E_g \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ characteristic of distorted octahedral Cu(II) complexes⁷.

The magnetic moment values of Co(II) complexes lie in the range 4.90-5.1 B. M. which is characteristic of high spin octahedral complexes. The electronic spectra of Co(II) complexes show two absorption bands at 8870 and 20000 cm^{-1} . The first band may be identified with the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ and the second band may be due to the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$. The absorption bands in the electronic spectra of Co(II) complexes are approximately similar to those reported for octahedral complexes⁸⁻¹¹.

The magnetic moment values of Ni(II) complexes are in the region 3.16-3.20 B. M. which show the presence of two unpaired electron. The values are typical of octahedral Ni(II) complexes. The electronic spectra of Ni(II) complexes show bands around 9300 cm^{-1} , 15750 cm^{-1} and 25974 cm^{-1} , characteristic of octahedral Ni(II) ion. These bands may be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(\nu_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)(\nu_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)(\nu_2)$, respectively.

The observed magnetic moment values of Fe(III) complexes are in the region 5.88-6.00 B. M. and support the octahedral stereochemistry of Fe(III)

complexes. The electronic spectra of Fe(III) complexes show a weak band around 9200 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^6T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^6E_g$ which is characteristic of high spin octahedral Fe(III).

Magnetic susceptibility measurements of the Mn(II) complexes at room temp. suggest that Mn(II) complexes are high spin and display magnetic moment values in the range 5.85-6.00 B. M. expected for five unpaired electrons in a weak octahedral field. The electronic spectra of Mn(II) complexes show four bands at 19800, 23000, 29000 and 34000 cm^{-1} . These bands may be assigned to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(D)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$. The magnetic moment values and electronic spectra support the octahedral configuration.

Fungicidal screening : All the complexes exhibited significant fungitoxicity at 500, 200 and 100 ppm, the inhibition ranging from 60 to 88%, 31 to 60% and 24 to 35%, respectively. The toxicity of metal chelates in the descending order is as follows:

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